

BUS TICKET ONLINE BOOKING SYSTEM

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Abstract. The Bus Ticket Online Booking System is a robotized stage that oversees different capacities related to bus ticket reservations. It handles all the forms included in booking bus tickets. This extension gives data on available buses, routes, schedules, and seat availability. It offers various adaptable and helpful highlights, permitting clients to book tickets and administrators to oversee bookings consistently and productively.

Keywords: bus, ticket, booking, system, administrators, clients

INTRODUCTION

In today's advanced age, the centrality of a Bus Ticket Online Booking System (BTOBS) cannot be exaggerated. Transportation administrations are advancing to meet advanced requests, making a productive BTOBS vital for overseeing bookings, progressing availability, and giving consistent client administrations. The system gives a centralized stage available over the web, permitting clients to get transport plans and book tickets remotely. One of the most important goals is to create a dependable, helpful, and exact booking framework. Hence, I plan a framework that can offer assistance in moving from physically overseen bookings to automated system, making the method more productive and compelling. This system will be helpful for clients who don't have sufficient time to visit ticket counters. It keeps a tremendous collection of transport courses, plans, and situate accessibility at the user's fingertip

PROBLEM

This system gives a helpful arrangement for travelers looking to book bus tickets online, making it less demanding to arrange trips without the bother of conventional strategies. Whether for day-by-day commuters or long-distance travelers, the system guarantees that clients can rapidly check accessible buses, select seats, and book tickets from their homes. Traveling effectively and comfortably could be a need for numerous travelers, and this framework permits them to book tickets with certainty and comfort. By streamlining the booking handle, travelers can dodge long lines and vulnerabilities related to overbooking. In expansion, the system guarantees that clients are well-informed about the accessible courses, plans, and estimating alternatives, making travel arrangements smoother and more dependable. This system is planned to meet the developing request for online administrations, giving a productive, user-friendly stage for transport travel.

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APPROACH

This system consists of two roles. There are Administrator and clients. Admin has extra functionalities to oversee transport benefit operations. After logging in, admins can add buses, upgrade schedules and route, and oversee all bookings.

In this system, the clients must log in to book ticket. After logging in, the client can look for buses and schedules. The client can at that point book tickets, see the booking history, and make payment. The system permits clients to select favored seats but does not give the alternative to cancel bookings. Figure 1 shows the admin and user system flow diagram, outlining authoritative capacities and data flow from the admin point of view.

Figure 1: System Flow Diagram

Figure 2: Database Design

An Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD) uses data modeling techniques to define business processes and form the foundation of a relational database. Attributes can be denoted as primary keys, which uniquely identify entities, or foreign keys, which link tables. Cardinality notation defines the relationships between entities. In this bus ticket online booking system, there are seven data tables: **buses**, **customers**, **routes**, **schedules**, **bookings**, **seats**, and **users**. Figure 2 illustrates the database design for these tables and their relationships.

RESULTS

After creating the system, system testing must be carried out to guarantee that it is free of bugs. If any bugs or mistakes are recognized amid testing, the designer must redress and settle them quickly. Testing includes assessing the program to distinguish contrasts between the given input and the anticipated yield. It surveys the system's quality, serving as both an approval and confirmation handle. Figure 3 outlines the execution of the system for the Bus Ticket Online Booking System.

The Web has become an imperative asset in present-day life; thus, the Bus Ticket Online Booking System has picked up importance from both the regulatory and client points of view. For administrators, the system creates modern openings to streamline transport administrations and operations, whereas, for clients, it makes comparing and

selecting transport plans and courses more helpful. According to an overview, most clients of bus ticket online booking system make choices incautiously and frequently choose to remain in a location within the first few seconds. Website plan plays a vital part in client maintenance; in case the plan is ugly or comparable to numerous other locales, clients are likely to take off and investigate other choices. Therefore, the venture has been outlined to supply clients with a simple route, speedy information recovery, and vital criticism instruments.

Figure 3: Implementation of this system

CONCLUSION

This system offers various preferences, such as lessening printed material, labor, and costs included in transport benefit operations, moving forward the exactness and quality of administrations, improving client fulfillment and comfort, encouraging the sharing and trade of ticket and planning schedules, making advanced records of bookings, and empowering inaccessible get to booking administrations. The Bus Ticket Online Booking System benefits both bus administrators, and users by making the whole preparation more proficient and user-friendly.

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